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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ABHAYASREE M bearing the USN 5SU19PT002 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ADITHYA M bearing the USN 5SU19PT003 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AHAMMED NASEEH V B bearing the USN 5SU19PT004 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AISHWARYA BIJUSH bearing the USN 5SU19PT005 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ALBIN JACOB VARUGHESE bearing the USN 5SU19PT006 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANAMIKA K bearing the USN 5SU19PT007 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANJANA MANOJ bearing the USN 5SU19PT008 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANJANA MOHAN bearing the USN 5SU19PT009 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANJIMA K V bearing the USN 5SU19PT010 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ATHIRA P KRISHNA bearing the USN 5SU19PT011 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AYESHA SAFEERA bearing the USN 5SU19PT012 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AYSHA FARHA bearing the USN 5SU19PT013 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. BAGHELE AISHWARYA RAJESH bearing the USN 5SU19PT014 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. BENECIA ANITA CARDOZO bearing the USN 5SU19PT015 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. BHAVYASHREE C VAIDYA bearing the USN 5SU19PT016 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. CHANNAMMA R NELAGUDDA bearing the USN 5SU19PT017 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. CHARAN JITENDRA VAIDYA bearing the USN 5SU19PT018 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. CHAUHAN KAVITA BABURAM bearing the USN 5SU19PT019 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DANY ELDHOSE bearing the USN 5SU19PT020 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DEEPTHI K J bearing the USN 5SU19PT021 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DI – ANN VERA VAZ bearing the USN 5SU19PT022 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DIAS RICHA CHRISTINE bearing the USN 5SU19PT023 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FARSANA T bearing the USN 5SU19PT024 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FATHIMA bearing the USN 5SU19PT025 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FATHIMA ARSANA bearing the USN 5SU19PT026 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FATHIMABI bearing the USN 5SU19PT027 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FINU ANTONY bearing the USN 5SU19PT028 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. GIFIN M PAUL bearing the USN 5SU19PT029 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. GOKUL A P bearing the USN 5SU19PT030 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. GREESHMA M EDWIN bearing the USN 5SU19PT031 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HARSHITHA G S bearing the USN 5SU19PT032 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HAZEBA FATHIMA bearing the USN 5SU19PT033 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HEMANTH A V bearing the USN 5SU19PT034 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HRUTHIKA M bearing the USN 5SU19PT035 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. IFTHISHAM bearing the USN 5SU19PT036 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JANE CARYN LOBO bearing the USN 5SU19PT037 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JILSHA P Y bearing the USN 5SU19PT038 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JITHIN T bearing the USN 5SU19PT039 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JOYCE MARIAM JOSY bearing the USN 5SU19PT040 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. KARUNA VISHRAM PARAB bearing the USN 5SU19PT041 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. KRISHNAPRIYA BIJU bearing the USN 5SU19PT042 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. LUGELLE MARIA DE GRACA FERNANDES bearing the USN 5SU19PT043 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MEHTAB JUBAPU SHUAIB bearing the USN 5SU19PT045 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MOHAMMED TAHA bearing the USN 5SU19PT046 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUHAMMED RASIL P M bearing the USN 5SU19PT047 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUHAMMED SINAN K bearing the USN 5SU19PT049 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUHAMMED SHANID P bearing the USN 5SU19PT050 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUHSIN K.P bearing the USN 5SU19PT051 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NEELINA K bearing the USN 5SU19PT052 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NIRMAL JAIN bearing the USN 5SU19PT053 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PEARL ASTIDA D'SA bearing the USN 5SU19PT054 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PUSHPA N NAYAK bearing the USN 5SU19PT056 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RAGHAVENDRA A N bearing the USN 5SU19PT057 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RATHIKA RAVINDRA NAYAK bearing the USN 5SU19PT059 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RAVI R H bearing the USN 5SU19PT060 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. REMYA RAVEENDRAN bearing the USN 5SU19PT061 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RIFNA KOUSAR bearing the USN 5SU19PT062 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RINSHIDA N P bearing the USN 5SU19PT063 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SAIDH ALI HAMZA bearing the USN 5SU19PT064 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SANDRA K R bearing the USN 5SU19PT065 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SANGAR SHIVANI NAVIN bearing the USN 5SU19PT066 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SANGEETH SANTHOSH bearing the USN 5SU19PT067 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SAYED FARZANA PARVEEN bearing the USN 5SU19PT068 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SEBINNABI TORGAL bearing the USN 5SU19PT069 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHAHISTHA BANU bearing the USN 5SU19PT070 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHAIKH SUMERA MEHEK NASEEM IRFAN bearing the USN 5SU19PT071 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHIFANA M E bearing the USN 5SU19PT073 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHRAMIKA bearing the USN 5SU19PT074 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHRIRAKSHA R ANGADI bearing the USN 5SU19PT075 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. STACY SANTAN FERNANDES bearing the USN 5SU19PT076 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SWETHA P S bearing the USN 5SU19PT077 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SYED MOHAMMED S J bearing the USN 5SU19PT078 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. TIDKE ANIKET NIRAJ bearing the USN 5SU19PT079 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. VARSHINI B bearing the USN 5SU19PT080 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. YASSER K V bearing the USN 5SU19PT081 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ZAHWA MUNEER bearing the USN 5SU19PT082 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a report on 10 asanas and their application in Physiotherapy”** in the fifth semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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